

Project Report

beelibre.lu - Luxembourg's open library of wild bee species profiles, pollen data, DNA barcodes and bibliographic references

António Jorge do Rosário Cruz^{‡,§}, Fernanda Herrera-Mesías^{‡,§}, Anna Hauprich^{‡,§,|}, Dylan Thissen^{‡,§}, Alexander M. Weigand^{‡,§}

[‡] Musée national d'histoire naturelle, Luxembourg, Luxembourg

[§] Fondation faune-flore, Luxembourg, Luxembourg

[|] University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart, Germany

Corresponding author: Alexander M. Weigand (alexander.weigand@mnhn.lu)

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Abstract

The ultimate goal of the beelibre project is to provide a kind of “one-stop-shop” online resource, hosting within a single multi-lingual website (beelibre.lu) relevant information concerning the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg. This website will provide free and immediate access to information on the taxonomy, natural history and geographical distribution of the over 350 species of wild bees species recorded in Luxembourg. For this purpose, four sections (a.k.a “libraries”) are hosted within the website: i) a database of high-quality images taken from live bees and museum specimens (for morpho-taxonomic identification and outreach); ii) a bibliographic repository of all nationally relevant publications (for metadata analysis and knowledge exchange), incl. short summaries; iii) a pollen inventory pilot experiment aiming to uncover potential ecological interactions between regional host flowering plants and their associated wild bee pollinators and iv) a DNA barcode reference library of wild bee species from Luxembourg currently lacking reference material in BOLD systems (for molecular taxonomic identification).

This initiative to produce and transfer knowledge about wild bees is aligned with Luxembourg's national action plan for pollinators and contributes directly to reducing knowledge shortfalls in relation to European bees. Therefore, all materials will be freely available to both researchers and the general public, socialising scientific knowledge to a wider audience and raising awareness on national pollinator biodiversity. With this initiative, we aim to provide a space that combines past efforts with current technology, building a platform that can be used to further assist and develop national conservation strategies protecting the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg.

Keywords

wild bees, taxonomy, public outreach, in situ photography, bibliography, images, pollen, DNA barcodes

Third parties involved in the project

Fondation-faune flore (FFF), National Museum of Natural History Luxembourg (MNHNL), Ministère de l'Environnement, du Climat et de la Biodiversité de Luxembourg (MECB).

Background

Wild bees are insect pollinators of fundamental relevance for both crops and wild plants. Their ecosystem services are valued in billions of euros and their disappearance could cause irreparable damage to biodiversity and human food production (Gallai et al. 2009, Vanbergen and the Insect Pollinators Initiative 2013). Swift action must be taken to prevent further declines on regional wild bee biodiversity, but the success of effective conservation strategies relies heavily on our understanding of wild bee taxonomy and ecology. For this purpose, well curated reference material plays a vital role. Other essential details such as high quality descriptions (extremely necessary for morphological identification in monitoring programmes), voucher specimens from natural history collections (important to address open research questions and for general educational purposes) and validated DNA barcodes (crucial for molecular identification of morphologically indeterminable cryptic species or complicated taxa groups) strategically represent the basis for a well-targeted study into the conservation of this zoological group, as well as its important ecosystem services. However, reliable reference data of all kinds for the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg is usually scattered and hard to find. Data regarding regional wild bee species diversity and distribution is spread amongst diverse sources, languages and media formats. In addition to several gaps regarding ecology, natural history and geographical distribution (Hortal et al. 2015), the lack of images, named Keartonian shortfall (Marshall et al. 2024), limits the recognition and identification of species in the field and affects the understanding and development of more explanatory and attractive keys for species identification. Moreover, despite the growing volume of DNA barcodes available in the Barcode of Life Data (BOLD) Systems,

misidentifications and gaps in the regional reference library constrain the detection capacity of DNA-based identification tools. Finally, the study of fine-scale ecological interactions between regional pollinators and their host plants, based on insect-focused approaches, is hard to develop due to a general lack of curated reference samples. These obstacles restrain our understanding of local wild bees and our capacity to propose well-informed conservation initiatives.

Relation to the funding programme

The beelibre project is closely linked to the following five actions mentioned in the [national pollinator action plan](#) ("*Plan national d'actions pour la préservation des insectes pollinisateurs. 2021-2026*") of Luxembourg:

- *C, Action 17 - Assurer un transfert des connaissances entre les acteurs du monde scientifique, les acteurs de la protection de la nature et les bénévoles* [English version: C, Action 17 - Ensure knowledge transfer between scientific stakeholders, nature conservation stakeholders, and volunteers]
- *C, Action 16 - Mieux faire connaître les insectes pollinisateurs sauvages* [C, Action 16 - Raising awareness of wild insect pollinators]
- *B, Action 12 - Améliorer les connaissances sur la diversité et la répartition des insectes pollinisateurs au Luxembourg* [B, Action 12 - Improve knowledge of the diversity and distribution of insect pollinators in Luxembourg]
- *B, Action 13 - Mettre en place un suivi systématique des insectes pollinisateurs à l'échelle nationale et sur le long terme* [B, Action 13 - Establish systematic monitoring of insect pollinators at the national level and over the long term]
- *B, Action 14 - Evaluer les risques d'extinction des insectes pollinisateurs sauvages* [B, Action 14 - Assess the risks of extinction of wild insect pollinators]

The beelibre project will also help to initiate further national research projects on wild bees (B, Action 15), to assist training courses and professional formations with reference data (C, Actions 20 & 21) and to select the wild bee species to be integrated into the updated regulatory conservation document, which is meant to explicitly comprise pollinators (A, Action 11).

Objectives, concept and approach

The aim of the beelibre project is to provide a kind of "one-stop-shop" hosting relevant information concerning the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg. The website will collate available and newly-generated information about appearance, ecology, distribution, taxonomy and conservation of the more than 350 catalogued wild bees (Reverté et al. 2023) in an open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) digital library.

Thus, all materials produced will be made publicly available to researchers, educators, stakeholders as well as to the general public, improving local knowledge on and socialising the wider public for this important pollinator group. For this purpose, four interlinked datasets ("libraries") will be generated, which likewise represent the project goals of beelibre:

- **Goal 1:** Image repository of the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg, including visualisations of living and pinned specimens (resulting in species profiles);
- **Goal 2:** Annotated list of bibliographic references dealing with the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg, incl., for example, first records and regional inventories;
- **Goal 3:** Physical pollen collection for the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg, originating from pollen loads carried by female wild bee specimens. Data will be depicted in an online catalogue for further distribution;
- **Goal 4 :** DNA barcode reference library of the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg, with curated and expert-validated genetic references for each species.

Concept

The project will develop an interlinked, comprehensive wild bee database for Luxembourg, combining expert validated taxonomic identifications, high-quality scientific images, relevant plant–pollinator interactions (via pollen data), literature resources, DNA barcodes and distribution maps. For targeted sampling of national wild bee species, the project will rely strongly on the biodiversity distribution data produced by the “Wild bee atlas of Luxembourg” (WBA) project, coordinated by the National Museum of Natural History Luxembourg (MNHNL). The beelibre project also aims to raise awareness regarding national wild bee biodiversity by releasing freely available materials that can be used by both experts and amateurs, as well as stakeholders developing outreach initiatives. Relevant information such as taxonomic descriptions, distribution data or ecological interactions between wild bees and their host plants will be translated in multiple languages (LU, EN, DE, FR) to make them more approachable to the international community of the country. Besides taking advantage of already collected specimens in the frame of the WBA project and specimens preserved in the collections of the MNHNL by previous studies, specimens of the national pollinator monitoring (MONIPOL), which is conducted by the Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), will be used to generate missing barcode references, collect pollen loads and feed the image repository. When no Luxembourgish specimens are available for a particular species, additional individuals may also be requested for morphological description from collections of cooperation partners, for example the Finnish Museum of Natural History (LUOMUS) or the German Barcode of Life Project (GBOL; Bonn and Munich).

Sampling strategy and in situ photography of living specimens

As a first step, it will be necessary to gain understanding of the number of extant wild bee species in Luxembourg in order to estimate the amount of work required for in situ photography of living specimens. Scientific articles will be essential for this, as was the study of taxonomic material deposited in the entomological collections of the MNHNL. Data extracted from important projects, such as the WBA of the MNHNL, will be also essential for directing our sampling effort, in order to increase our efficiency in terms of richness of species recorded/photographed, as well as profiling our list of priority species. Other studies into the ecology and natural history of the species found in Luxembourg will be also very important. Understanding the seasonal period of regional occurrence, the microhabitat, the type of plants/flowers used as resources, the type of soil or material used for nesting, parasites or possible hosts, as well as other factors, such as rarity or relative abundance of populations (when available), finally will make our fieldwork more efficient and objective.

Wild bee surveys to imaging living specimens will be conducted during spring and summer by trained specialists and local helpers. Most of the fieldwork will be conducted between 9 am and 6 pm, with at least two researchers. To photograph the wild bees, we will use Mirrorless and DSLR cameras, combined with a macro lens (Table 1). We anticipate to photograph the wild bees both foraging in their natural environment (Fig. 1) and in the mini-studio with the white background (Fig. 2). For the photographs in natural environments, the best results will be obtained in the early morning or on cloudier/colder days, where the bees move more slowly and are more tolerant to our presence. In addition, the natural light will be more appropriate for this type of photography. However, photographs on a white background will always have a priority. This is because it is not always possible to know the taxonomic identity of the specimen without capturing it first for morphological analysis. For this purpose, active sampling using hand nets will be used to collect specimens without damaging them. The captured specimens will be cold anaesthetised, with the use of a thermal bag of approximately 10°C. At this temperature, the bees temporarily reduce their movement, which will facilitate their handling for taking more detailed pictures of relevant morphological traits, confirm preliminary taxonomic identification and collect pollen samples (see protocol in Suppl. material 1) from females.

Table 1.

Different cameras and lenses that were used to photograph wild bees during the Beelibre project.

Camera	Type	Sensor	Lens
Canon R5	Mirrorless	45 MP, Full frame	RF 100 mm, F2.8L, Macro IS USM
Canon 90D	DSLR	32.5 MP, APS-C	EF 100 mm, F2.8, Macro
Fujifilm X-H2S	Mirrorless	26.1 MP, APS-C	XF 80 mm, F2.8, R LM OIS WR Macro

Once the bees are removed from the thermal bag, they will be transferred to a mini studio with a white background, where we will choose three types of prioritised anatomical

poses for imaging: one frontal, one lateral and one from the apex. However, we also will take photographs of the dorsal, ventral or other particular anatomical parts that could help us identify the specimen later. From these photos, it is often possible to confirm the identification to species level while still in the field. If the morphological identification requires the use of more sophisticated equipment (i.e. species that can only be discriminated by male genitalia or cryptic species that can only be separated by DNA etc.), after the photographs, the specimens will be killed by freezing and stored for later laboratory analysis. In this case, special care will be undertaken to collect only the specimens that are strictly necessary, minimising the use of lethal sampling. Additional individuals of selected species will also be collected in the field to produce COI barcodes for the BOLD systems reference library.

Upon conclusion of this project, all our decisions related to photographic documentation will be used to develop a protocol, where we will list our best decisions, as well as the adaptations made to obtain the best results. This protocol will be published in scientific journals or other scientific media, thus contributing to a better discussion about new methods and techniques used to sample wild bees.

Laboratory analysis

All collected specimens will be prepared and pinned at the Scientific Research Center (SRC) of the MNHNL. The pinning will be done by taking care that all parts of the insect are arranged within the same focal plane for subsequent indoor photography. Pollen loads from females, either newly collected in the field or from available natural history collections, will be removed before preparation and stored separately as a physical voucher available for associated projects to develop further research (e.g. pollen metabarcoding, pollen grain image classification, microbiome analysis).

For wild bee specimens, traditional identification will be done by a taxonomic expert (FHM) using a stereomicroscope and morphological keys. In case of particularly challenging morpho-identifications, resulting in no definitive species level assignment, one middle leg will be taken for DNA barcoding following the protocols described in Weigand and Herrera-Mesías (2020). The same procedure will be followed if a particularly rare species with no or very few barcodes in BOLD systems is detected via morphological analysis, so new COI barcodes can be generated and uploaded to the reference library. All wild bee barcodes produced by this process will be made publicly available and voucher specimens will be stored in the dry-pinned entomological collection of the MNHNL.

Macrophotography of pinned specimens

Pinned specimens reliably identified to species level coming from the MNHNL collection, the wild bee atlas, partner institutions or resulting from new field sampling in the course of this project will be prepared for macro-photography. The pinned specimens will be

photographed at the SRC using a high resolution camera combined with a macro lens as well as a Keyence VHX-S660E digital microscope.

Basic imaging considering three angles (front, lateral and dorsal view) against a white background will be undertaken for all specimens using a macro lens mounted on a high-resolution camera (for maximum resolution and detail). Relevant characters for morphological species diagnosis and particularly small specimens will be photographed using the digital microscope to reach sufficient magnification. In case no individuals from a particular species are found in the field or amongst local available sources, dry-pinned specimens may be requested for photographic documentation from partner institutions (i.e. the Finnish Museum of Natural History). The resulting photographic gallery will be combined with the *in situ* pictures to create a repository of reference images accompanied by taxonomic descriptions that will be released directly at the beelibre.lu website. All images will be licence-free and publicly available for scientific and educational purposes.

Preliminary results

Results of the Beelibre project are available on the project website www.beelibre.lu (Figs 1, 2).

Figure 1.

Wild bee species photographed in natural environments during the Beelibre project:

a: *Anthidium oblongatum*; [doi](#)

b: *Bombus pascuorum*; [doi](#)

c: *Halictus scabiosae*; [doi](#)

d: *Megachile willughbiella*. [doi](#)

Figure 2.

Wild bee species photographed against a white background during the Beelibre project:

- a: *Andrena haemorrhoa*; [doi](#)
 b: *Anthidiellum strigatum*; [doi](#)
 c: *Bombus pratorum*; [doi](#)
 d: *Seladonia subaurata*. [doi](#)

Impact

A successful development of the beelibre.lu online repository will directly address the following (sub)actions and indicators as mentioned in the [national pollinator action plan](#) for Luxembourg:

C, Action 17 - Assurer un transfert des connaissances entre les acteurs du monde scientifique, les acteurs de la protection de la nature et les bénévoles

Indicators: number of training courses, interested naturalists and specialists.

All four types of libraries (images, literature, pollen, barcodes) provided by the beelibre project would contribute to the further development of an informed and engaged national community, by creating a space for the transfer of scientific knowledge regarding wild bee identification and conservation to the general public.

C, Action 16 - Mieux faire connaître les insectes pollinisateurs sauvages

Indicators: number of participating parties.

The open access to the image library containing the species images and profiles would provide illustrative material for outreach and awareness-raising campaigns, as well as to develop teaching material, for example, for LUGA2025, science weeks, educational programmes of nature parks or the Pollinator Academy on international level.

B, Action 12 - Améliorer les connaissances sur la diversité et la répartition des insectes pollinisateurs au Luxembourg

Indicators: number of datasets, bibliographic library.

Besides the diversity and distribution data on wild bees, which are collected in the WBA project of the MNHNL, 'beelibre' would collate and make publicly available relevant literature, images and barcode references for the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg. This would facilitate the work of researchers and stakeholders interested in developing conservation strategies targeting regional wild bees. Furthermore, the to-be-compiled pollen repository will make it possible in the future to develop sophisticated taxonomic analysis, such as DNA metabarcoding, thus to increase the ecological knowledge of especially "data-deficient" wild bee species.

B, Action 13 - Mettre en place un suivi systématique des insectes pollinisateurs à l'échelle nationale et sur le long terme

Indicators: national survey installed, nationally coordinated regional inventories and monitorings, citizen-science projects.

The 'beelibre' project offers a wide range of open source image and literature data, which would help to increase general knowledge on wild bee pollinators in Luxembourg, but in particular, would also support the morphological identification of wild bee species by national actors and the public consulting the species profiles. Furthermore, the generated barcode reference library would point to problematic, i.e. cryptic species and, thus, flag those species complexes for DNA-based identification.

B, Action 14 - Evaluer les risques d'extinction des insectes pollinisateurs sauvages

Indicators: Red List of wild bees, wild bee species assessed on the Red List.

The collated bibliographic information and pollen data would provide information on ecological links between host flowering plants and their associated pollinators, thus to assist the assessment of wild bee species in the context of Red Lists. DNA barcode data would provide insights into cryptic species complexes being present in Luxembourg, for example, thus to aid (morpho)species Red List evaluations. Automatically updating distribution maps embedded in the species profiles will help to get an understanding about the distribution and rarity of individual species.

Timeline

The six work packages (WP) of the beelibre project are organised in two types: production and management. The first four work packages and their associated teams will focus on producing and collating the data that will support each fundamental pillar of the project (image gallery, bibliographic repository, pollen collection and DNA barcode reference library). They involve all activities leading to the production of content (i.e. such as fieldwork, development of visual records, laboratory analyses or bibliography compilation). The WPs 1-4 will be developed simultaneously all throughout the project and some overlaps are expected between their activities. However, they will be led by independent PIs that will oversee the tasks within their assigned WP and make sure they are completed during the estimated times of the project. The remaining two work packages, WP5 and WP6, will focus on managing all necessary information, budget, assets and human resources for the overarching successful development of the project. They oversee all logistic activities relevant to the development of the beelibre database, as well as the communication of outputs to the target audience and associated institutions (i.e. organisation of meetings and presentations, curation of results and outreach activities). These packages will be active only at specific times during the project and their main tasks will be to coordinate the input received from all involved parties and to organise it in a way that ensures the clear transmission of the results obtained. The synergy between both types of WPs will ensure that all necessary steps are fulfilled to produce and manage the foreseen results.

WP1 - Image database

Images of living and preserved (i.e. dry-pinned) specimens for all (extant) wild bee species of Luxembourg will be collated in a single database. Field pictures and basic shots considering the three main angles (front, lateral and back view) will be taken for all available wild bee species (Figs 1, 2). Simultaneously, the availability of photographs from other wild bee projects, as well as from other MNHNL partners and collaborators will be assessed (Task 1.1). In conjunction with this strategy, we will establish an initial priority list of bees to be photographed in the field and in the laboratory (Task 1.2). This priority list is not fixed and is always updated according to the availability of images from collaborators (Task 1.1), the existence of the species in the collections of the MNHNL and its collaborators, the occurrence of the species according to the seasonality presented by its natural history, genus or particular ecological functionality presented. Bees that occur in a short timeframe, for example, are prioritised. Specimens of the dry-pinned collection of the MNHNL, from private collections of *collaborateurs scientifiques*, international collaborators (e.g. Finnish Museum of Natural History), as well as from ongoing national wild bee studies (e.g. MNHNL wild bee atlas and MONIPOL) will be used and imaged by means of a Keyence VHX digital microscope available at the MNHNL (Task 1.3). Images of living specimens will be done by explicitly visiting known populations of the target species and by involving passionate citizen scientists and *collaborateurs scientifiques* of the MNHNL (Task 1.4). All material photographed will be processed and organised on SSD cards (backups), with the respective data regarding day, location, species name, sex

etc. During this process, we will check the species identification and select the photos to be edited.

- T1.1 Evaluation of image data already present for the Luxembourgish wild bees;
- T1.2 Setting up a priority list of wild bee species to be photographed (species, gender, dry-pinned/living, specific traits);
- T1.3 Imaging of species on the priority list (collection material);
- T1.4 Imaging of species on the priority list (living material).

WP2 - Bibliographic library

Knowledge of the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg is available, but widely scattered in diverse literature sources, languages and formats (e.g. more recently Rasmont et al. (2017), Schneider (2018), Vereecken (2018), Weigand and Herrera-Mesías (2020), Cantú-Salazar et al. (2021), Herrera-Mesías and Weigand (2021), Siebenaler et al. (2021), Siebenaler et al. (2022)). Additionally, not all information has been published in journals and a large body of “grey literature” exists (e.g. master theses, datasets of LIST etc.). In WP2, available bibliographic references on the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg will be collected and the major information extracted in a short summary and presented on a single multi-lingual website (Task 2.1). For all literature records possible, we will also upload and freely provide the PDF file and - if needed - digitise hard-copy documents (Task 2.2). A SensiShot archive scanner that can be used for this purpose is available at the MNHNL.

- T2.1 Compilation of available bibliographic references on the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg;
- T2.2 Digitisation of hard-copy documents and upload to website.

WP3 - Pollen repository

Several wild bee species are oligolectic and show a strong preference for one or a few selected groups of flowers, collecting pollen to feed their offspring. At the same time, around one third of all wild bee species in Luxembourg lack sufficient knowledge about their ecology or pollen preference and are classified as “data deficient” (preliminary data MNHNL). In WP3, female individuals from target species found in the field carrying pollen loads will be captured and pollen samples will be taken from them for long term storage (Task 3.1-a). All pollen samples will be kept at -20°C in a freezer. Relevant metadata, including associated wild bee species, will be taken to curate an in-house pollen repository for subsequent analysis.

Additionally, the repository made out from living specimens will be complemented with samples from natural history collections (Task 3.1-b). The information regarding the pollen repository will be ultimately made available to other researchers as an online

catalogue via the currently developing DiSSCo RI (www.dissco.eu) of which the MNHNL is the national node (Task 3.2), so partner institutions can request pollen samples of interest for more detailed ecological analysis, for example, pollen DNA metabarcoding (Bell et al. 2017, Lucas et al. 2018, Baksay et al. 2020, Gous et al. 2021, Lowe et al. 2022) or visual pollen classification, based on machine-learning approaches (Viertel and König 2022), benefitting future research on regional plant-host interactions. Laboratories that have requested pollen samples from the catalogue for further analysis will be asked to share their identifications with the beelibre.lu webmaster, so the content of the website can be updated accordingly.

- T3.1 Curation of a physical pollen repository;

a) collection of pollen from living specimens) collection of pollen from historical specimens;

- T3.2 Compilation of a digital pollen catalogue.

WP4 - Barcode library

Modern molecular techniques for species identification, such as DNA barcoding and metabarcoding, crucially rely on well-curated and comprehensive DNA barcode reference libraries. Only in case a DNA barcode reference is available and the taxonomic status of each sequence verified, comparisons of unknown sequences against this molecular taxonomic backbone library will yield correct and trustworthy identification results.

A preliminary analysis of DNA barcodes available for the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg has shown that 97% of the species already have public barcode references (Herrera-Mesías et al. (2022)). This barcode coverage analysis will be repeated in the context of the [beelibre](http://beelibre.lu) project (Task 4.1). In WP4, we want to add barcodes of the missing 3% of the species (i.e. 11 species), but also verify existing and add further barcodes for species which are not comprehensively covered (i.e. having 1-4 barcodes or barcodes only from very distant locations; n = 42) (Task 4.2). Pinned and wet material of the MNHNL collection will be analysed for DNA barcode generation, but also freshly collected material of the WBA project of the MNHNL and the MONIPOL project of LIST (both 2019 - present) integrated (Task 4.3). The MNHNL will make sure to have a valid wild bee sampling permission for the entire period of the [beelibre](http://beelibre.lu) project. All barcodes will be made publicly available in the open access Barcode of Life Data (BOLD) system (Task 4.4). The ultimate goal of this WP is to compile a most comprehensive and curated DNA barcode library for all wild bees catalogued for Luxembourg (Task 4.5). DNA barcoding of wild bees is well established at the MNHNL and the laboratory protocols of Weigand and Herrera-Mesías (2020) for DNA extraction, polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and sequencing will be followed. An ABI Sanger sequencer is available at the MNHNL directly. This WP will be conducted in-kind at the MNHNL (all consumables and staff costs covered) and students involved conducting their BSc and MSc theses and internships.

- T4.1 DNA barcode gap analysis of DNA barcodes available in BOLD;
- T4.2 Validation of available DNA barcodes in BOLD;
- T4.3 Generation of DNA barcodes from missing species, based on new or historical material;
- T4.4 Upload of newly-generated DNA barcodes to BOLD;
- T4.5 Compilation of a curated DNA barcode library for national wild bees.

WP5 - Communication and outreach

The four libraries, which are central to the beelibre project (i.e. wild bee images, bibliographic repository, pollen catalogue and DNA barcodes), will be accessible under a single open-access web address (www.beelibre.lu). This platform will be hosted and maintained by the MNHNL. Regular updates will be performed on an annual basis, but much more frequently during the initiation of the website. The content will be presented in four languages (Luxembourgish, French, German and English).

- T5.1 First release of beelibre.lu website;
- T5.2 First annual update of the website;
- T5.3 Final project release.

WP6 - Project management

The activities and progress of the first four working packages will be monitored by the team of WP6. All necessary information regarding important research outputs, budget, assets and human resources will be managed by this WP. This package is also responsible for keeping the core team up to date regarding logistic decisions and communicating pertinent information to partner institutions within the framework of the project.

Project meetings will be held on a quarterly basis amongst core team members and an annual strategic and budget meeting for all involved parties is planned by the end of the year each December.

- T6.1 Hosting of quarterly meetings;
- T6.2 Yearly progress report/presentation.

Sustainability

Upon completion of the project, we will have organised the largest and most complete database concerning the wild bees of Luxembourg, both from a morphological and

genetic point of view, as well as a pollen repository, yielding the potential to uncover relevant interaction networks with plant-hosts. Improving the access to secure, organised and up-to-date knowledge regarding local wild bee species is one of the main goals of the beelibre project. Therefore, its primary and secondary contributions will continue to support this goal after the main project has ended.

Primary contributions

Scientific profile image database

In addition to scientific data and taxonomic descriptions, the photographic documentation of national bee species available at the beelibre.lu website would be a great aid to conservation efforts. Since, in addition to presenting the identity of each species, photography has the power to increase knowledge and interest in wildlife, in addition to enhancing the emotional appeal, awareness and concern related to nature conservation.

In the future, all materials will be available to stimulate and implement ideas related to biodiversity conservation. Amongst the beneficiaries, schools will be able to use our database to prepare materials for classes; NGOs and government platforms can use this material to design environmental education and nature conservation programmes; books on zoology, ecology and biodiversity conservation will have faithful and high quality content and images; species identification keys can be made more attractively with clear illustrations; photographic exhibitions on the importance of insects, pollinators and biodiversity will have more attractive, high-quality content - all of which will be free of charge. Since it is meant to provide automatically updating distribution maps along the individual species profiles (as already implemented on the www.neobiota.lu website), distribution data of the Luxembourgish wild bees can be considered also up-to-date even after the projects lifetime, given that observation records are uploaded to the database of the MNHNL, GBIF or via the iNaturalist.lu web application.

Bibliographic library

Information about wild bees of Luxembourg is dispersed in different articles, books, reports and projects - and in different languages. Gathering this information in a single place will facilitate access for researchers and enthusiasts, reducing the time to find relevant, reliable and quality references. Therefore, beelibre.lu will be able to promote and enhance future projects and activities, serving as an important source of credible information for any type of project involving the national wild bee fauna of Luxembourg. New literature items will be uploaded as well.

Pollen repository

The pollen repository will be kept at the Scientific Research Center of the MNHNL and the online catalogue will remain active after the end of the project (ensured by the Museum's involvement into DiSSCo, www.dissco.eu). Partner institutions will be able to request

samples for their own projects at any given time. Future collaborations and joint publications with laboratories within the national territory and with international research institutions are foreseen to develop based on this initiative. Further research activities incorporating the data and samples stored at the repository will help us to better understand the ecological and evolutionary processes that regulate the interactions between pollinators and host plants. Furthermore, it has enormous potential to clarify which species are key to agricultural and natural ecosystems, identifying which species are effectively specialists or generalists or which we should direct greater efforts towards their conservation.

DNA barcode library

All barcodes produced by the beelibre project will be freely available in BOLD systems, benefitting also colleagues based in other research institutions. Once the project has reached its end, this well-curated regional database for the wild bee fauna of Luxembourg, comprising a few but, high quality entries per species, will be available for future studies and more sophisticated molecular analysis.

Secondary contributions

As the original photographic material will be kept within the intranet of the MNHNL, once the project comes to term, it will be possible to prepare a selection of the most representative wild bee images taken in the field. The selected images can be displayed as fine art prints in a temporary exhibition focusing on the national wild bee biodiversity at the MNHNL. The exhibition would include a description of the wild bee species depicted in the photographs, their distinctive traits, types of behaviour and their relevance to their ecosystem. This would be an excellent opportunity to engage people of all ages, increasing their interest in wildlife and to inspire them to further develop awareness and concern for biodiversity and nature conservation.

Topics to be addressed may include the different wild bee morphotypes found in the national territory, social v/s solitary bees and plant-pollinator interactions. The photographic gallery can be accompanied by interactive material (e.g. pinned bees, 3D models, pollen slides, dried nests, local host-plants), audiovisual sources (e.g. footage of field activities, audio records of humming bumblebees and short clips following foraging bees) and summer workshops targeting the general public (e.g. basic wild bee identification, wildlife photography, insect-friendly gardening and appropriate nest box building). Additionally, the images could be used to prepare printed material for distribution at the MNHNL describing national wild bees and encouraging visitors to make use of the beelibre.lu website.

Furthermore, unreleased material could be used in collaboration works with international partner institutions, to support local itinerary exhibitions or even be submitted to competitions aiming to display selected works in public spaces, such as the annual FNR Science Image Competition.

The output of the beelibre project can be used in multiple ways to promote actions aiming to raise the awareness and appreciation of regional wild bees, keeping people involved in the protection of pollinators in Luxembourg and the Greater Region and stimulating strategies for their conservation. In turn, this will also help to secure the long term-sustainability of our wild pollinators for generations to come.

Communication, dissemination and visibility

With this project, we aim to communicate the importance of wild bees to the Luxembourgish environment and ecological services. Our project offers the possibility to involve in the process participants from a broad range of disciplines and areas, including educators, researchers, NGOs and governmental institutions, amateur entomologists and conservationists, as well as the general public. Therefore, in addition to an easy-to-navigate website, we will have several communication and dissemination activities, with the aim of maximising our visibility in these different niches, such as research conferences; networks and social media; dissemination in local or international radio and newspapers; photo exhibits at the MNHNL, ecological walks and presentations, as well as dissemination campaigns with varying degrees of interactivity.

Scientific Papers and Conferences

The MNHNL is a well-regarded institution that has a long history of scientific collaboration housing a substantial part of Luxembourg's natural bio- and geoheritage in its diverse collections. Both new researchers and partners from other institutions will be able to have access to our data repository and the beelibre libraries. In addition to publicising the beelibre website, members of our team will participate in national and international scientific conferences, with the main objective of presenting relevant findings and networking, potentially securing new collaborations and encouraging other institutions to incorporate the construction of similar databases amongst their project tasks.

Mass media appearances

Newspapers and radio channels already have dedicated audiences and established social media; we would take advantage of these pre-existing channels to foster our project's visibility, as well as the conservation of wild bees and subsequent protection of the ecosystem. Once the foundations of the project are established, beelibre's outreach coordinators will undertake the role of creating all the conditions for their participation in radio programmes. During these broadcast appearances, team members will share with the host and the public details regarding the beelibre project main activities (e.g. field work, laboratory work, collection curation etc.) and most important results, acknowledging the contribution of collaborators, supporters and financing institutions.

Social Media Networks

Social media today is an important tool for scientific outreach. In addition to being an interactive tool, it offers a differentiated dynamic in the sharing of information, even allowing direct communication between the disseminators and the audience. The beelibre project will have a profile created on Instagram, where various information about the project will be published. The primary focus of social media posts will be on the work carried out on Luxembourgish wild bee species. Other content related to the importance of pollination and conservation of these species will also be published periodically.

Social Events and Community Outreach

Activities to engage the general public in a more direct way will also be considered during the time-frame of the beelibre project. Such activities will be scheduled for special occasions and will aim to reach out to the local communities, thus to raise awareness about wild bees and inspire citizens to learn more about them, leading into discussions and encouraging positive behaviour towards our regional wild bee fauna. These activities can be done either as an open participation workshop or webinar that can be pre-announced through the MNHNL social media channels and agenda for key dates such as world bee day (20th May), world environment day (5th June) or in the context of the bi-annual Science Festival and FNR Researcher's Days, as well as annual Naturmusée festival.

Preliminary results

Regionally, the data extracted from the project has been extremely important for drawing up Luxembourg's first Red List of wild bees, contributing more than 2000 geographical occurrence points of species, amongst other relevant information. In addition, the project has made several important records for native bees, extending their known geographical distribution and confirming the occurrence of several species for the first time in the national territory.

With regard to the communication, socialisation and dissemination of scientific knowledge, our project has participated in and given some workshops and guided tours, presentations and photographic exhibitions. Through the production of content for social media, the project has also been increasing visibility about the diversity, ecology, natural history, taxonomy and conservation of wild bees, on a profile with over 300 followers on instagram.

At an international level, the project has helped to compile a list of European wild bee species (Reverté et al. 2023), contributing new records and expanding the distribution of some species. Due to the visibility of the project, several partnerships, mainly aimed at identifying wild bee species, developing sound tools, 3D images and training new taxonomists (EPIC-consortium), are in the process of being developed with other institutions and universities in different countries.

Below are some of the events attended or organised by the beelibre project.

International scientific events:

1. XII European Congress of Entomology, Crete, 16-20 October 2023 (Greece);
2. Guest lecture Universidad Central del Ecuador (UCE) 9 January 2024 (Equador);
3. 92. Deutschsprachige Imkerkonferenz, Luxembourg, 5-7 September 2024 (Luxembourg);
4. XIII Congreso Nacional de Entomología Aplicada – XIX Jornadas Científicas de la SEEA, 7-11 October 2024 (Spain);
5. Südwestdeutscher Insektenkundetag, Mainz, 19 October 2024 (Germany);
6. Benelux Zoology Congress, Mons, 12 and 13 December 2024 (Belgium).

Workshops and courses in Luxembourg:

1. Orchids and Pollinators (MNHNL); 27 May 2023;
2. Pfaffenthal Pollinators, Jardin de canopée; 3 June 2023;
3. Pinning course (MNHNL); 14 March 2023;
4. Créer une mosaïque de biodiversité (MNHNL); 25 May 2024;
5. Pollinators walk - Finding connections in nature and city (Cooltur); 7 July 2024;
6. FNR Researcher's Days (Rockhal, Belval); 28-30 November 2024.

Art exhibitions:

1. Belle étoile exhibition "bee essential"; 25 January to 10 February 2024;
2. MNHNL, Réunion des collaborateurs scientifiques; 16 March to 14 May 2024;
3. Transitions Days Festival (Schluechthaus, Hollerich); 28 to 30 June 2024;
4. Nature Musée Fest (MNHNL); 15 September 2024;
5. Rainy Days Festival (Philharmonie Luxembourg); 20-24 November 2024;
6. FNR Researchers' Days (Rockhal Luxembourg); 28-30 November 2024.

Budget

The beelibre project is an initiative proposed by the Fondation faune-flore (FFF) alongside the National Museum of Natural History Luxembourg (MNHNL), supported by the Government of Luxembourg through the funding line "Pollinisateurs" of the Ministère de l'Environnement, du Climat et de la Biodiversité. The project was awarded an initial budget of €293,095 by the first funding call of the national pollinator action plan (version 2022).

Most of this budget was allocated to support staff members with specialised skills (i.e. taxonomic expertise, background in scientific photography and laboratory skills), as well as to provide short-term work experience opportunities in applied entomology and taxonomy to early career researchers (Table 2). The rest of the budget is meant for purchasing new equipment to process photographic material, prepare outreach workshops or cover participation fees in conferences and symposia, key aspects to

improve the visibility of the project, as well as to represent the local perspective in ongoing discussions on pollinator decline.

Table 2.

General overview of the items and categories considered by the granted project budget.

Items	2023	2024	2025	Comments
Full-time staff	111,764.00 €	110,005.64 €	28,000.00 €	Staff members in charge of the main deliverables of the project.
Temporal staff assistance	461.25 €	29,861.11 €	8,954.15 €	Short term employees, freelance workers and interns.
Consumables and travel	768.50 €	1,680.28 €	1,600.00 €	Storage, equipment and materials for workshops and outreach activities. Travel, accommodation and allowances to attend scientific conferences are considered as well.

Monitoring of project performance

Project performance indicators are presented for each work package separately.

WP1 – image database

- compilation of priority list;
- number of photo sessions in the field (+number of total photos);
- number of photo sessions in the laboratory (+number of total photos);
- number of missing species photographed alive;
- number of missing species photographed for diagnostic characters (pinned);
- number of total images available/species covered at the website (species profiles).

WP2 – bibliographic library

- number of bibliographic references located;
- number of bibliographic references uploaded (and potentially digitised).

WP3 – pollen repository

- total number of pollen samples archived;
- number of species for which pollen samples are available;

- number of “data deficient” species with pollen samples available;
- total number of pollen records digitised in the online catalogue.

WP4 – barcode library

- compilation of priority list for DNA barcoding;
- total number of DNA barcodes generated and uploaded;
- number of DNA barcodes for species so far lacking any DNA barcode;
- number of DNA barcodes for species having only 1-4 DNA barcodes.

WP5 – communication and outreach

- availability of the first version of the website;
- number of website updates;
- number of outreach activities.

WP6 – management

- number of quarterly meetings and budget evaluations;
- number of annual progress presentations.

Funding program

Luxembourg's first funding call on pollinators within the "[Plan national d'actions pour la préservation des insectes pollinisateurs. 2021 - 2026](#)" opened in 2022.

Grant title

beelibre.lu - Luxembourg's open library of wild bee species profiles, pollen data, DNA barcodes and bibliographic references.

Hosting institution

National Museum of Natural History Luxembourg (MNHNL).

Ethics and security

We make it clear that we have no commercial commitments whatsoever with the companies that manufacture the products used in the field and/or photographs taken in the laboratory.

Part of this work involves capturing, handling and sometimes collecting some wild bee specimens. These methods are invasive and, therefore, require a team with experience in handling specimens. It is also important to obtain prior permits for techniques involving the capture, handling and collection of wildlife specimens. All the data and specimens collected and photographed will be deposited in the entomological collection of the National Museum of Natural History Luxembourg (MNHNL).

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Beelibre protocol for pollen sampling and storage. [doi](#)

Authors: Beelibre team

Data type: Workflow and steps to collect and store pollen samples obtained from living specimens

Brief description: Custom-made pollen sampling protocol.

[Download file](#) (133.69 kb)